

HALMSTAD UNIVERSITY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Sweden is generally considered a strong case in relation to gender equality policy in general and for policies on gender-based violence (GBV) specifically. From a policy perspective, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and reprisals in the workplace (including academic organisations and in relation to students) have been regarded as forms of discrimination and as such are regulated through the Swedish Discrimination Act (in addition to such violations that are regulated in the penal code). The obligation to apply preventive measures, regularly examine risks, undertake measures, and remedy or take action against suspected cases is regulated in law and includes an obligation for employers and education providers to collaborate with employee and student representatives. This means that all HEIs in Sweden at the institutional level are bound by the law to work to prevent and to handle cases. HEIs are also obligated to work against victimisation and workplace bullying and to prevent and handle threats, crises, and emergency situations through the Work Environment Act. Through the government mission on gender mainstreaming (JIHU¹), all HEIs are furthermore obligated to work with gender mainstreaming in order to realise Sweden's overarching gender equality objectives, one of which is: 'Men's violence against women must stop. Women and men, girls and boys must have the same rights and opportunities to physical integrity.' There are also general protections for human rights advocates that aim to prevent the harassment of those who actively work to promote human rights more generally and there is a comprehensive penal code in which GBV is addressed (see the country report for Sweden, Callerstig 2021).

There is no exact information on how many HEIs have policies and guidelines on sexual harassment, even though, according to the law, all of them should. An investigation into compliance with the Discrimination Act and with the requirement to apply active anti-discrimination measures at Swedish HEIs was conducted by the Swedish Equality Ombudsman in 2019-2021.

¹ JIHU=Jämställdhetsintegrering i högskolor och universitet in English GMA Gender mainstreaming in Academia, see Country Report Sweden: <https://zenodo.org/record/5534004#.YeqlwvjTVD8>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The university has a set of three general policies addressing gender-based violence (GBV):

- 1) Guidelines Regarding Discrimination and Harassment (hereafter 'the Guidelines')
- 2) Student Policy - We Make Each Other Better! Rules and Expectations Linked to the Study / Work Environment (hereafter called 'the Student Policy')
- 3) Policy for the Working Environment and Equal Rights and Opportunities (hereafter called 'the Lika villkor policy')

The rector has the ultimate responsibility and must ensure that policies and guidelines for the work environment and for ensuring equal working conditions are followed in daily operations. Everyone at the university has a responsibility to contribute to and work to create a good work environment in accordance with the systematic work environment management and the university's procedures and guidelines. Managers and employees are responsible for including a gender equality perspective in daily operations. There is a coordinator for equal opportunities and equal treatment (Lika villkor) who is responsible for coordinating work according to the Discrimination Act. There is also a programme manager for the university's work with gender mainstreaming, who is responsible for supporting this work in both the core and support activities. The programme manager performs, among other things, university-wide gender equality analyses within the framework of the university's quality assessments, and contributes to the work of gender mainstreaming by integrating documents, procedures, and processes. The programme manager is linked to a network that is made up of representatives of the university's four academies. Halmstad University is revising its guidelines regarding harassment, sexual harassment, bullying/victimisation and reprisals, and these guidelines apply to the entire university.

URLs

- › Guidelines Regarding Discrimination and Harassment: <http://dokumentarkiv.hh.se/api/showDocument/EC34DA92-8577-4232-A499-99CF072155D6>
- › Student Policy – We Make Each Other Better! Rules and Expectations Linked to the Study/Work Environment: <http://dokumentarkiv.hh.se/api/showDocument/5AC2E146-BA88-41AE-B728-0F7613F9C923>
- › Policy for the Working Environment and Equal Rights and Opportunities (Lika villkor): <http://dokumentarkiv.hh.se/api/showDocument/5D755A03-BD8D-4B11-8924-A107AF09F5DE>

Entry into force: The Guidelines entered into force in 2011, while the other two policies entered into force in 2020.

TRAINING

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The three policies combined address the following **five** forms of GBV: psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and economic and financial violence. The Lika villkor Policy focuses on sexual and gender-based harassment, while the other two policies address the five forms of GBV cited above.

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The three policies combined address the following **5Ps**: protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnership, and policy. The Lika villkor Policy does not address any Ps, while the other two policies address protection, prosecution, and provision of services. The Student Policy is the only policy that addresses partnership. The Guidelines is the only that addresses policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

Lika villkor policy

Academic staff, non-academic staff, and students

Guidelines

Academic staff, non-academic staff, and students

Student policy

Students

The three policies combined address all three target groups and do not identify any other groups. The Student Policy is the only policy that focuses solely on students.

Intersectionality addressed: No.

Specific vulnerable groups: The Lika villkor Policy does not address any vulnerable groups. The other two policies address the same **six** vulnerable groups: staff and students with disabilities, staff and students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ staff and students.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Guidelines make clear that all staff and students are obliged to act if they witness an incident. The document reads: 'Everyone who has the university as their workplace has a joint responsibility for the work environment and to say no if there is discrimination or harassment.'

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Student Policy reads: 'If you as a student violate the above, the incident will be investigated and disciplinary measures, such as a suspension or warning, will be considered.'

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Guidelines set out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigating cases of violence among students and staff.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, responsible persons/units, the description of the investigation procedure and sanctions.

Who to contact and how to report: The Guidelines state: 'If, within the university's operations, you feel that you are being discriminated against or harassed, you should, if possible, clearly tell the person who is discriminating against you. Record the events that you perceive as discriminatory or harassment, stating the time and place, and, if possible, a co-worker or student you trust about the incident. This is important if you want to take the matter further and if your statements do not suffice. If you are a student and feel discriminated against or harassed, you should contact someone you trust at the university, in the student union, or the student department. You can also choose to submit a written report to the principal. If you are an employee and feel discriminated against or harassed, you should first contact your boss. You can also contact your trade union organisation, a work environment representative, or HR. You can also choose to submit a written report to the rector. (...)'

Responsible persons/units: Vice chancellor, disciplinary committee or personnel responsibility committee, discrimination ombudsman.

Description of the investigation procedure: 'According to the Discrimination Act, both employers and education providers are required to investigate and take measures if they become aware that an employee or a student claims to have been subjected to discrimination or harassment. The university must then investigate the circumstances without delay. In cases where a report is received by the vice chancellor, a formal administrator and a legal expert are appointed by the head of administration. According to the Work Environment Act, the employer must investigate and put an end to bullying / victimisation (this applies in the case of both employees and students). If signs of bullying / victimisation appear, countermeasures must be taken and followed up on as soon as possible. The incident must be investigated quickly and legally. The requirement of legal certainty means that the person in question in the investigation must always be regarded as innocent as long as the investigation does not lead to the opposite conclusion. However, the documents that are prepared within the framework of the investigative work in this step become public to a significant extent when the case is concluded. The university must take other measures that can reasonably be required to prevent the behaviour from continuing. The measures taken shall, as far as possible, be taken in consultation with those who have claimed to have been harassed. A support person must always be offered to both parties, i.e. the person who claims to have been harassed and the person or persons who are considered to be the harasser. Both those who claim to have been harassed and those who have been accused of such misconduct must be given the opportunity to state their version of what happened, and the university must make it clear that behaviours that offend others are unacceptable. If written documentation is available from the person who has claimed the harassment, this should be handed over to the investigator as part of the investigation. If the alleged perpetrator is the victim's direct superior, then the alleged perpetrator's superior must take the place that the victim's superior would otherwise have occupied in the investigation.'

Sanctions: 'When the investigation is completed, the rector will take a position on how the case should be handled further and will then decide either:

- that the case be concluded without further action,
- that a warning be issued by the rector to the student who is harassing,
- that an oral statement be made by the rector to the employee who is harassing,
- that the case be referred to the disciplinary committee or the personnel responsibility committee for review.

If the rector decides that the case should be sent for review by the disciplinary committee or personnel responsibility committee, the following applies:

If a student is accused of harassment, the possible consequences, according to chapter 10 of the Higher Education Ordinance, are a warning or suspension from the study programme for a maximum of six months. If an employee is accused of discrimination or harassment, the possible consequences are a warning, a pay deduction, suspension, or dismissal. Finally, a violation implies that there is a justified suspicion that a crime has been committed (e.g. sexual harassment) and there is then a possibility of legal prosecution. If the obligation to investigate in conformity with the Discrimination Act is not fulfilled and is executed at a substandard level, the university may be ordered by a court to pay discrimination compensation to a person who has been subjected to harassment.

5.1 Follow-up on cases

The responsible manager must ensure that the harassment has ceased. This shall be done through follow-up discussions with both the victim and the alleged perpetrator. The purpose shall be to ensure that the unwanted behaviour has ceased and that the working environment for both

the victim and the alleged perpetrator is acceptable. The manager must document that the follow-up interviews have taken place.

6. For persons dissatisfied with the university's management:

Persons not satisfied with the university's handling of claims of discrimination and harassment can contact the discrimination ombudsperson (DO)² or the Swedish Work Environment Authority.³ Anyone who has been discriminated against or harassed at work and is a member of a trade union should turn first to the union instead of the DO. Finally, there is also an opportunity to bring an action against the university in the district court.'

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Anne-Charlott Callerstig in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

² www.do.se

³ www.av.se

